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Research Article

INFLAMMATORY BOWEL DISEASE: CLINICAL ASPECTS AND TREATMENTS

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Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) is a chronic inflammation of intestine which occurs due to host microbial interactions. These interactions occur in a genetically susceptible person. Both the small and large intestine are affected by inflammation and are characteristics of autoimmune disease; IBD. In this disease, body's own immune system attacks the elements of the digestive system. This inflammation encompasses two major forms of diseases, ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease. Abdominal symptoms are prominent in patients affected by these diseases like abdominal pain, diarrhea, vomiting, and bloody stools. Moreover, other defects like intestinal epithelial barrier function decline are also observed. In this review paper the types and symptoms of IBD are described. Then the diagnosis methods and available treatment options are discussed.

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INTRODUCTION:

Primary diseases included in the inflammatory bowel disease are Crohn's disease and ulcerative colitis. In Crohn's disease, anywhere along the GIT line inflammation is caused, while in ulcerative colitis inflammation is only in some parts of GI tract mainly in the colon, but it is long lasting. Exact etiology of IBD is not clearly known but it is believed that several factors become the cause of the development of these group of diseases, which include (but not limited to) change in the immune system, genetic variation and bacterial contamination. For example, mutation in gene NOD2 can produce proinflammatory cytokines and worsen the IBD. Along with genetic factors, environment also plays a significant role. Moreover, studies have shown that industrialized nations are more prone to these diseases. High consumption of milk protein, animal protein, tobacco and polyunsaturated fatty acids also increase the risk of IBD and Crohn's disease. ¹

Treating IBD include the usage of anti-inflammatory drugs like 5 aminosalicylic acid, to reduce colon lining inflammation. Patients with severe IBD are also treated with infliximab. Infliximab is a monoclonal chimeric antibody which works against a cytokine (TNF- α) involved in inflammation of the intestine. Many other immunomodulatory drugs like thalidomide is also used. However, under specific circumstances, surgery might become compulsory if medicine fail to treat the inflammation. This operation is commonly called as colectomy and in it the large intestine is removed. In ulcerative colitis, the disease cures after the removal of colon; but in Crohn's disease unfortunately the disease can still reoccur after surgery. ²

Most pharmaceutical compounds, given to treat IBD, have side effects like nausea, diarrhea, and headache which can sometimes worsen the

situation by reducing patient compliance. Therefore, it is mandatory to abide by the limitations and carefully monitor the issues associated with the treatment of IBD. One recent promising tool is, microencapsulation which allows the target delivery of medicine compounds with in the time dependent fashion. ^{3,4}

Types and Symptoms of IBD

The nature and location of inflammation, aids in differentiation of Crohn's disease and ulcerative disease, which otherwise have similar characteristics. The difference between these two is that, in ulcerative colitis inflammation is localized to the colon/ large intestine, while in Crohn's disease it can affect any part of the GI tract. In industrialized countries, the prevalence of Crohn's disease is higher. It is estimated that 30 to 50 persons out of 10,000 people can get affected. While talking about the microscopic level, entire bowel wall is affected by Crohn's disease, while in ulcerative colitis, the inflammation is restricted to the epithelial lining of the gut. ⁵

Success of medical treatment entirely depends upon the use of anti-inflammatory and immunosuppressive drugs. Although the use of later drugs like methotrexate, and azathioprine usage is a challenge for physicians as these are effective but comes with a cost of side effects. For example, the administration of these compounds can cause insomnia, weight gain, fluid retention, hypertension, constipation, drowsiness, and vomiting. Therefore, focus is on the formulation of new treatment methods with minimal side effects for IBD patients is under research. ⁶

Symptoms vary from patient to patient depending upon the disease term and condition. A comparison of ulcerative and Crohn's disease is shown below in the table:

Key Features	Crohn's Disease	Ulcerative Colitis
Location		
Upper parts of GIT	Rarely	Never
Distal ileum	Very common	Never
Colon	Common	Always
Rectum	Rarely	Never
Signs and symptoms	Pain in the lower right abdomen, swelling, thickening of the bowel wall	Pain in the lower left abdomen, diarrhea, rectal bleeding, weight loss

Diagnosis of IBD

Several tests, methods and techniques are available to diagnosis IBD in patients. One of these techniques include capsule endoscopy for the effective diagnosis of Crohn's disease. For this technique it is mandatory that the colon is clean, for this patient's are asked to consume safe drinking formulation. The capsule is in the size of pill, has the ability to take pictures of the inner layer of gastrointestinal tract, when orally taken. Then the endoscopic images obtained can help in identification of inflammation of localized ulcerations and small erosions prominent in the GIT. Radiology tests are an alternate of endoscopy, these also help in the diagnosis of the disease.⁷

For instance, a barium follow through process is effective for Crohn's disease, when the target location is only small intestine. In this procedure, patient is a given a solution of barium sulfate to drink, this appears white on X-ray imaging and shows the internal bowel lining. Another technique includes blood tests. Laboratory blood tests can reveal increased white cell count, and sedimentation rates, as these both are linked with inflammation of the intestine. B12 deficiency and autoimmune hemolysis can also be diagnosed by complete blood cell counts for IBD patients. Moreover, for differentiation of ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease and IBD diagnosis, increase amount and levels of serological markers might also be helpful.

Biopsies can also aid in confirmation of the disease, as it is quite helpful in diagnosis and differentiation of the inflammation. Transmural pattern of inflammation if often observed in Crohn's disease, which means that inflammation may go deep down in the intestinal wall. Under microscopic biopsy, the affected region may show mucosal damage with focal infiltration of leukocytes into the epithelium.⁸

X-ray linked tomography and MRI are also commonly used for diagnosis of IBD intra-abdominal complications like fistulae, small bowel obstruction, or abscesses. Computed tomography is a method in which multidetector scanners with high temporal and spatial resolution is used for complete visualization of mucosa, small bowel and lumen. It can aid in the detection of the severity of the inflammation, submucosal fat deposition, fibrofatty proliferation and sacculations. Sacculations results from chronic inflammation and submucosal fat deposition depicts past inflammation, which leads to fibrosis and asymmetric mesenteric border shoertening of the wall.⁹

Major Treatments

- Medication for IBD

No specific medical or surgical treatment is available for IBD, as the exact reason for its cause isn't known. Treatment of this disease includes the use of anti-inflammatory and immune modulators depending upon the symptoms of the disease and type of inflammation. For instance, 5-aminosalicylic acid, and immune modulators like mercaptopurine, azathioprine, certolizumab, infliximab, methotrexate, adalimumab, and natalizumab. Th2 mediated response is triggered by these compounds that dampens Th1 mediated inflammation. This causes the production of anti-inflammatory cytokines like IL-4, IL-5, IL-6, and IL-10 that suppress the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines. Oral administration has observed with positive outcomes, but its administration doses have certain limitations.¹¹

- **Monoclonal Antibodies**

For the treatment of IBD anti- TNF- α antibodies are frequently used, and these are able to decline the amount of TNF- α in the body. Recent research ahs depicted that a monoclonal antibody, infliximab, is effective in Crohn's treatment as it neutralizes the TNF- α by preventing its interaction with the receptor. The complementary relationship between the infliximab and TNF- α molecule is a promising Crohn's treatment and other autoimmune disorders. However, some limitations do exist for its usage, as it can develop tuberculosis which is owing to the neutralization of TNF- α . Delayed hypersensitivity reactions are also an outcome of this antibody administration. Other antibodies like certolizumab and adalimumab have also shown positive outcomes.^{9,10}

- **Drug Loaded Microcapsules**

One of the promising tool for the treatment of IBD is artificial cell microencapsulation, that allows the exact point and time dependent delivery of the medicine. It involves the preparation of artificial structures made up of different protein and polymer types. A variety of molecular structures, like drugs, enzymes, DNA, bacterial cells, antibodies, mammalian cells and other microorganisms.¹²

Use of alginate polylysine-alginate (APA) microcapsules are also under consideration and acts as an efficient platform for fine delivery of medicinal compounds. APA microcapsules are ionic interaction formulation between alginate molecules (negatively charged) and calcium ions (positive molecules). Preliminary research has shown that these capsules, under low pH environment remain intact and encountered in the stomach. In the SI, these capsules gradually degrade and release medicine in time-dependent fashion.¹³ The in vivo biocompatibility of these microcapsules has shown that they have no clinical toxicity.

CONCLUSIONS:

Although, the study shows that no specific cure is there for IBD, but several pharmaceutical compounds are able to reduce the intestinal inflammation and bring the issue under control. This review has provided a holistic overview of experimental studies based on anti-inflammatory and monoclonal drugs. Most of the studies which encapsulated the use of anti-inflammatory drugs has shown that these have positive outcomes and can inhibit the proliferation of cytokines like IFN- γ and TNF- α , but sadly these also come with side effects like nausea, vomiting and abdominal pain.

However, appropriate use of artificial cell microencapsulation, promising results can be obtained as these have no clinical side effects and enhance the reduction of intestinal inflammation. But, many questions still exist and this technique is under trial with different component composition. More research is needed to finalize it as a safe treatment for IBD patients with different types of inflammation.

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